

MAPPING RECONSTRUCTION OF GAZA TO OVERCOME DONORS' FATIGUE

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Abstract

As the world witnesses the ongoing War on Gaza, characterized by mass displacement and widespread destruction that is never preceded in modern human history, this situation prompts urgent questions about the future mapping of reconstruction efforts. The challenges, timelines, key actors, and crucial elements for effective, human-centred recovery become complex, yet essential to be tackled with defined problem-solving techniques to avoid fatigue of donors. The continued military campaign has resulted so far in over 38,387 Palestinian deaths, more than 92,058 injuries, and the destruction of over 60% of buildings, making the area virtually uninhabitable. While the extent of future destruction remains uncertain, planning for post-conflict reconstruction is vital. This involves learning from past efforts and challenges to shape effective future strategies. Taking into consideration that Gaza has been under prolonged occupation and wars in the last two decades that ended with multiple incomplete reconstruction attempts. The authors study the unprecedented destruction since October 7th, 2023 and comparing the past strategies and other post-war rebuilding efforts. The implication of the study is s emphasises key factors that need to be taken into consideration when shaping Gaza's upcoming reconstruction strategies by all the concerned players.

Keywords: *War on Gaza, Reconstruction Mapping, Donors Fatigue, Palestine.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

As the world witnesses the genocide in Gaza, the mass displacement and the massive destruction that has reached nearly everything, turning the Gaza Strip into an unliveable place. One can only think, once that all ends, what will the plan be for reconstruction? How difficult and timely will it be? Who will be the main actors, and what key elements need to be considered for effective and human-centred recovery? Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2024)

As the Israelian genocidal military campaign continues against the Palestinian people in Gaza, the fatal human and capital loss continues, resulting in the killing of over 38,387 Palestinians and injuring more than 92,058 Palestinians(PCBS, 2024) and the destruction of over 60% of the buildings making Gaza strip practically uninhabitable(ReliefWeb, 2024). It remains unclear how much more destruction Gaza will endure before peace is restored or what kind of society will emerge post-conflict. Despite these uncertainties, planning for the post-conflict reconstruction phase is crucial, as it examines past efforts, challenges, and outcomes to shape effective future strategies.

The Gaza Strip, under Israeli occupation and subject to ongoing conflict and destruction over the years, has seen multiple incomplete reconstruction efforts. Learning from past experiences is vital to build on existing opportunities and address previous failures.

Studies analyzing reconstruction efforts, most recently after the 2021 conflict, have identified major barriers such as the Israeli blockade, exclusion of Gaza stakeholders, and short-term humanitarian donations lacking clear planning (Barakat et al., 2024; Milton et al., 2024; Barakat and Shaban, 2015). However, under the recent genocide that started on October 7th and the massive destruction that has been taking place for more than eight months, a radical change in the recovery plan must take place or else no tangible results are expected to be achieved. In a best-case scenario where construction materials are delivered five times as fast as in the 2021 war, rebuilding destroyed homes might be done in 2040 (UNESCWA and UNDP, 2024).

This study aims to contribute to the literature on reconstruction efforts by analyzing past strategies and post-conflict rebuilding in other countries. It will consider the new context after October 7th and the main influencing factors shaping the upcoming reconstruction phase in Gaza.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Review of Gaza Infrastructure Condition before the October 7th, 2023.

Israel has occupied Gaza and the West Bank, including East Jerusalem, since June 1967. Despite Israel's "withdrawal" from Gaza in 2005, since Hamas took over in 2007, Israel has maintained tight control over the territory through a land, air, and sea blockade. For nearly 17 years, Gaza has been almost entirely cut off from the rest of the world, with severe restrictions on the movement of goods and people. This blockade, combined with Israeli military operations, has had serious implications for the population of Gaza, which is one of the most densely populated areas in the world, with 2.3 million people living in a 363 square km area under chronic conflict conditions (UNCTAD, 2024).

Since 2007, several Israeli military operations have taken place in Gaza, notably in 2008, 2012, 2014, 2021, 2022, May 2023, and October 2023. These operations have caused hostilities, internal displacement, and recurrent destruction of critical infrastructure, services, housing, facilities, and livelihoods necessary for the basic functioning of society. A summary of the cost of damage per military conflict is outlined in Table 1.

The situation for Gazans has not improved an inch for more than a decade. The electricity is out most of the time, the border to Egypt is closed most of the time, Israel continuously blocks the import of construction materials, most salaries remain unpaid or delayed, and relations between Fatah and Hamas are hostile, with both parties blaming each other for the reconstruction failure. Besides, Gaza's economy remains captive to the Israeli market.

Felsberger, S. (2015)

Key economic indicators before and after the blockade highlight the de-development of Gaza. At the time of establishing the Palestinian National Authority in 1994, Gaza had about the same standards of living as the West Bank. The ratio of Gaza's GDP per capita to that of the West Bank fell from parity in 1994 to 44 per cent in 2007, reaching 28 per cent in 2022 (UNCTAD, 2024). Before October 7th, socioeconomic conditions in Gaza were already deteriorating, with the unemployment rate among the highest in the world, reaching 46% in

2022 compared to an average of 34.8% in 2006. Youth unemployment (ages 15-29) reached 62.5% during the same period (PCBS). Additionally, 31% of households in Gaza had difficulties meeting essential educational needs such as tuition fees and books due to a lack of financial resources. 1.3 million People (62%) required food assistance, 1.48 million registered as refugees, and two-thirds of the population lived in poverty, almost 80% dependent on international aid.

Infrastructure and services were far from meeting basic needs; in 2021, only 50% of the electricity demand in Gaza was met, with average power cuts lasting 11 hours per day, and 78% of piped water was unfit for human consumption (OCHA, 2022).

Table 1: Summary of the Impact of the Previous Military Wars in Gaza 2008-2023

Year	Palestinians killed	Palestinians injured	Housings destroyed or damaged	Displaced people	Total cost of damage (million USD)
2008- 2009	1385	5,380	60,000	20,000	2.5 B
2012	168	1046	10,000	-	2.7 B
2014	2251	11,231	171,000	100,000	
2021	261	2211	12,558	117,000	108 m
2022	49	383	1471	-	
May 2023	34	190	2943	1244	-

Ref: Authors developed from UN_reports on the damage assessments of wars (UNDP, UNCTAD & OCHA data on casualties)

As observed in Table 1, Gaza has been subjected to six significant conflicts between 2008 and 2023, in addition to over 30 separate Israeli military operations and assaults. Between 2008 and 2023, a total of 4,000 people were killed, and more than 20,000 were injured, with direct costs exceeding 5 billion dollars. It is important to note that much of the damage from past conflicts remains unrepaired, with limited access to construction materials and critical equipment since 2007, further delaying the repair and upgrade of homes and infrastructure needed to address high population growth and recurrent destruction.

Summing up, prior to October 2023, Gaza was already in a vicious cycle of conflict, restricted access, and lack of resources, severely undermining the quality of life and prolonging the humanitarian crisis. These accumulated impacts were further compounded by the conflict that erupted in October 2023, bringing about a devastating toll on the Gaza Strip.

Felsberger, S. (2015) questioned why it became almost impossible to break the cyclical destruction and reconstruction, manifested in almost all the Israeli atrocities in Gaza and subsequent international assistance. He studies the destructive aspects of reconstruction attempts in Gaza, shows the structural problems in international aid, and is emblematic of the overall approach of international actors to the Palestinian struggle for justice and liberation.

2.2 Preliminary Assessment of the Direct Damage to Gaza's Infrastructure due to War on Gaza since October 2023.

With Israeli military operations ongoing in Gaza for more than eight months, obtaining accurate assessments of the hostilities and physical damage is challenging. However, preliminary assessments covering a short period reveal unprecedented devastation that continues to increase daily (The World Bank, 2024; UNCTAD, 2024).

By July 2, 2024, at least 38,387 Palestinians had been killed, 92,058 injured, and at least 360,000 housing units damaged (PCBS). With 6% of Gaza's population either killed or injured,

no other armed conflict in the 21st century has caused such a devastating impact on a population in such a short timeframe (UNESCWA, 2023). Furthermore, the reported death toll likely underestimates the true number, with many bodies buried in the rubble, potentially exceeding 10,000 people at least (UN office Geneva, 2024). Additionally, indirect health complications from the conflict may surpass direct violence, with indirect deaths from reproductive, communicable, and non-communicable diseases potentially ranging from three to fifteen times the number of direct deaths (Geneva Declaration Secretariat, 2008).

On the capital destruction side, the World Bank's Interim Damage Assessment indicates that as of the end of January 2024, direct damage to Gaza's infrastructure is estimated at approximately \$18.5 billion, equivalent to 97% of the total GDP of the State of Palestine in 2022. Damages are primarily concentrated in residential buildings (72%) and commerce, industry, and services (9%), with the remaining 19% affecting other critical infrastructure sectors such as education, water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH), health, energy, information and communication technology (ICT), municipal services, and transport. The destruction and damage to physical infrastructure amount to \$341.2 million for education (schools and universities), \$503.7 million for WASH, and \$553.7 million for health facilities, directly affecting the provision of basic needs in Gaza (The World Bank et al., 2024).

The level of destruction in Gaza is such that rebuilding public infrastructure would require external assistance on a scale not seen since 1948. Even with an optimistic scenario in which a five-fold increase in construction materials is allowed into Gaza, reconstructing the destroyed housing units would take until 2040 (UNESCWA and UNDP, 2023).

Figure 1: Proportion of estimated total damages per sector (The World Bank et al., 2024)

On socioeconomic conditions and service delivery, according to projections from the latest Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC, 2024), famine is imminent, with 1.1 million people, half of Gaza, experiencing catastrophic food insecurity, and the entire population is experiencing acute food insecurity and malnutrition. Palestinians in Gaza now constitute 80% of all people facing famine or severe hunger worldwide with over 60% of the population already living under the poverty line prior to October 2023 according to the IMF (2023).

Health service delivery is experiencing major disruptions, with nearly 84% of health facility buildings destroyed or damaged, Shorrab et al. (2024). The remaining facilities lack access to medicines, ambulances, basic lifesaving treatments, electricity, and water. The education system has completely collapsed, with all children out of school and most schools being used as shelters for internally displaced people (IDPs). An estimated 17,000 children have been separated from their families, rendering them particularly vulnerable to various forms of exploitation and abuse. Therefore, Phusavat and Buheji (2024) called for ensuring that the displaced learners are considered even during reconstruction. Besides, the pervasive trauma linked to the ongoing violence has severely deteriorated mental health, especially among vulnerable groups such as women, children, the elderly, and persons with disabilities (The World Bank et al., 2024).

2.3 Factors that Will Influence the Reconstruction Efforts taking the context of post October 7th, 2023 events.

2.3.1 Recognition of Palestinian Rights by the International Community

The escalation of tensions and violence post-October 7th has significantly increased international attention on Palestine. Mass demonstrations are still ongoing in many Western countries as a matter of advocacy on the governments, universities, and other institutions to stop their support to Israel. At the same time, multiple European countries have recently recognized the State of Palestine, namely Norway, Ireland and Spain, reaching 146 countries worldwide that recognize the state of Palestine (Aljazeera, 2024).

This renewed focus could play a pivotal role in the future of Gaza's reconstruction. When the international community prioritizes the Palestine issue, it can lead to increased diplomatic efforts and funding for reconstruction projects. Advocacy from global solidarity movements and the media's extensive coverage can amplify the need for humanitarian assistance and development initiatives in Gaza. Additionally, the involvement of key regional players in diplomatic negotiations could facilitate smoother implementation of reconstruction efforts by addressing political and logistical challenges.

2.3.2 The Unprecedented Attack on the UNRWA

The United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees (UNRWA) has faced severe challenges, including funding cuts and political opposition, which directly impact its ability to operate. As the agency provides essential services like education, healthcare, and emergency relief, any reduction in its capacity can severely hinder reconstruction efforts. This threat is highlighted by Israel's efforts to advance a bill that designates UNRWA as a terrorist organization. The bill also calls for the closure of UNRWA offices in Israel and applies the provisions of the Penal Code related to "terrorist organisations" to the UN agency. From the other side, the United States House of Representatives has approved a bill that would ban funding for the UNRWA amid the humanitarian catastrophe in Gaza (Aljazeera, 2024).

If the UNRWA continues to face attacks and funding shortfalls, it may struggle to support the population's basic needs, let alone contribute to long-term rebuilding projects. Conversely, a reaffirmation of international support for the UNRWA could ensure the continuation and expansion of its programs, which are crucial for stabilizing and rebuilding Gaza.

2.3.3 The US Presidential Election

The upcoming US election holds significant implications for Gaza's reconstruction. The foreign policy stance of the new administration will shape the level and nature of US involvement in the Middle East, including financial aid and political support for reconstruction efforts in Gaza. A government supportive of increased aid and diplomatic engagement could accelerate reconstruction by providing the necessary resources and political backing. On the other hand, an administration less inclined to support Palestinian causes could slow down reconstruction efforts by limiting funding and international diplomatic support. The election also influences Congressional support, which is crucial for sustaining long-term aid programs and ensuring consistent policy towards Gaza. Hochberg (2016) mentioned that insufficient investment not only slows down the reconstruction but leaves Gazans with a dangerously low quality of life till another war erupts.

2.4 Factors that would help Stipulate Gaza Reconstruction Outcomes

Gaza has been living under an unusual siege environment for a long time, and this made reconstruction difficult in the aftermath of its three destructive wars, even before the War of October 7th 2023 starts. Therefore, Barakat et al. (2020) found that research on sieges tends to concentrate on the coping strategies of besieged communities, humanitarian issues associated with the impacts, humanitarian access, and the prioritisation of needs, with little or no attention paid to reconstruction.

Reconstruction outcomes have varied over time due to the inability to stipulate four key factors: time, needs, scarcity, and political context. Barakat et al. (2020) mentioned that through the analysis of these variables, the efficient and effective large-scale reconstruction of Gaza has never been actualised.

Barakat et al. (2018) called for a review of the bureaucratic Gaza Reconstruction Mechanism while assuaging Israel's security concerns. The mechanism introduced new bottlenecks that are impeding effective reconstruction and have institutionalized and depoliticized the siege of the Gaza Strip by passing the responsibility for its maintenance on to the international community.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Based on the review of Gaza's infrastructure condition before the October 7th, 2023, a preliminary assessment of the direct damage to Gaza's infrastructure is done using the literature provided by the main players from the international agencies. The review also considers factors that will influence the reconstruction efforts taking the context of post-October 7th, 2023 events.

Considering all this, the authors start evaluating the past reconstruction methodologies and the post-War socioeconomic possible human factor issues related to any reconstruction plan for Gaza. Buheji (2024)

4.0 APPLICATION & ANALYSIS

4.1 Past Reconstruction Methodologies and Results

The goal of this section is to reflect on past rounds of reconstruction in Gaza to understand the main challenges and how they were addressed, and to highlight the factors influencing future reconstruction strategies in the context following October 2023.

4.1.1 Donor Gaza Reconstruction Conferences

In previous reconstruction phases, donor conferences were typically held after reaching a ceasefire, coordinated by the donor community. The most critical dilemma facing Gaza's reconstruction efforts has been and remains one of legitimacy and control. While the Palestinian Authority (PA) is recognized as the legitimate authority by the international community, including Egypt and Israel, Hamas has effectively controlled the Strip since 2007. Despite this, actual control of access and resources is largely in the hands of Israel, which, under international law, remains the occupying power in Gaza. Israel fears that Hamas will use reconstruction funds for rearming and rebuilding its defences. Consequently, Hamas has been excluded from all reconstruction discussions and coordination efforts. This exclusion, combined with the lack of a national coordinating body and PA control in Gaza, and the Israeli blockade, has rendered reconstruction efforts ineffective, slow-paced, and inadequate, resulting in accumulated destruction with each Israeli War.

The main finding from past reconstruction efforts is not just the exclusion of Hamas but also the exclusion of local representation from Gaza, including non-governmental organizations, civil society organizations, and the private sector. This exclusion was evident not only in international conferences, but also the needs and damage assessments, such as those conducted in 2009 and 2014. As a result, reconstruction plans were mostly externally led, without real inclusion of local needs and priorities, affecting the Gazans' acceptance of the outcomes and their ability to hold others accountable throughout the reconstruction process (Barakat and Shaban, 2015).

4.1.2 Conditionalities Donations and Lack of Accountability

Another key challenge was the political conditionalities and lack of accountability for donations. Many donors attached conditions to the funding pledged. For instance, during the 2009 conference, a \$900 million from the U.S. government pledges was conditional to the Palestinian Authority coalition government between Fatah and Hamas to recognize Israel's right to exist. Similarly, Gulf States conditioned their pledges to Palestine to complete reconciliation between Fatah and Hamas. Aside from the fact that these conditions seemed implausible to be achieved with no tangible progress on the reconciliation over the years, it was also one-sided, with support to Palestine conditional on factors not entirely in their control, whilst support to Israel remained unhindered by any mechanisms of accountability for its actions in the West Bank and the Gaza Strip. The absence of such accountability only serves to exacerbate the complex reality of aid in Palestine (Barakat and Shaban, 2015).

4.1.3 Donors Fatigue

Donor fatigue has been a persistent issue over the years in Gaza, where the cyclical nature of destruction and rebuilding since 2008 has led to hesitation among donors to commit to long-term reconstruction projects. Despite concerns, significant external resources were still mobilized after each conflict. However, the lack or absence of donors was prominent in the post-2021 and 2022 wars.

While some pledges of assistance for reconstruction followed the 2021 war, almost no pledges were made in the month following the 2022 war. The total amount pledged equals about 25% of the total amount pledged post-2014 (Milton et al., 2024). This reduction in funding can also be attributed to external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war, which redirected international aid towards supporting Ukraine militarily and responding to the resulting humanitarian crisis, in addition to the indirect impact of the War on global supply chain disruptions and rising commodity prices, particularly energy and construction materials.

4.2 Socioeconomic Issues Related to the Reconstruction of Gaza

Gaza does not need physical reconstruction; it needs healing plans that bring in social divides, help build trust in institutions, and lay the groundwork for durable development. After hostilities cease in Gaza, many challenges are expected to emerge. These challenges would consist of a complex interplay of humanitarian, socioeconomic, and political factors. These challenges can be both immediate and long-term, affecting not just the direct recovery from the War on Gaza, but also the broader process of issues related to reconstruction, such as the social capital of the Palestinians in the strip. Buheji and Hasan (2024)

4.2.1 Humanitarian Challenges and the Need for National Reconstruction Plan

Displacement and homelessness are expected to be the major problems related to reconstruction, where the significant displacement is alarming since many families lost their homes and even relatives besides the entire neighbourhood. People are expected to stay busy ensuring access to food, clean water, and healthcare where these infrastructures are damaged.

While there should be plans for reconstruction, there should be parallel efforts to meet the demand for addressing, repairing, or creating rehabilitation for the psychological trauma that almost all the Gazans have gone through. Based on this, Gaza would need a national reconstruction plan that prioritises the most necessary infrastructure and reconstruction that would help the community heal and develop. It should be based on the optimisation of specific constraints that would alleviate the suffering step by step and eliminate it over the year. This should be taken into consideration, as rebuilding essential infrastructure, such as roads, schools, hospitals, and utilities, is a significant task.

This means we need to work on restoring livelihoods and economic structures, including markets and businesses, in parallel, which is crucial for long-term stability. Addressing also the environmental damage caused by the devastating destruction and atrocities done is important. This means we should consider environmental pollution when dealing with unexploded ordnance and rubble removal, besides the necessary health and safety requirements. Buheji and Al-Muhannadi (2023), Enshassi (2000).

4.2.2 Social and Political Challenges before and during Reconstruction Efforts

The social and political challenges require that the reconstruction efforts are designed based on social cohesion that fosters a sense of community and addresses grievances that the conflict may have exacerbated. These challenges also require the reconstruction to be based on effective governance and legal frameworks that ensure enough security, justice, and human rights.

These social and political challenges require effective and coordinated delivery of international aid to address humanitarian and reconstruction needs.

4.2.3 Refugees and Internally Displaced Challenges

Managing the return of refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) safely and dignifiedly should also be part of the reconstruction plan. Rebuilding the socioeconomy and providing employment opportunities, especially for those displaced, is critical to prevent despair and instability. This requires transitioning from emergency aid to sustainable development to ensure long-term economic stability.

Rebuilding schools and ensuring children return to education to prevent a lost generation would be part of educational and cultural reconstruction that would help to address one of the main needs of the refugees and the internally displaced.

4.2.4 Reconstruction of Cultural Heritage Sites

Part of the reconstruction efforts plans should focus on protecting and restoring cultural heritage sites that may have been damaged or neglected. The reconstruction of Gaza must also prioritize preserving and restoring its cultural heritage sites. These sites are significant for their historical and cultural value and play a crucial role in the identity and resilience of the Palestinian people. The destruction of cultural heritage can profoundly impact the community's sense of history and continuity, making their restoration a vital component of the overall reconstruction efforts.

Cultural heritage sites in Gaza, including historical buildings, religious sites, museums, and archaeological sites, are integral to the cultural and historical identity of the region. These sites witness Gaza's rich history and diverse cultural influences over millennia. Preserving them is essential for maintaining the cultural memory and identity of the Palestinian people.

Restoring cultural heritage sites in War-ridden area presents unique challenges. Many of these sites may have suffered extensive damage since October 7th, 2024; requiring specialized restoration techniques and expertise. Additionally, the ongoing War and limited access to materials and skilled professionals further complicate restoration efforts. Ensuring the security and protection of these sites during the reconstruction process is also a significant concern.

The restoration of the sites should start by conducting thorough assessments and documentation of the damage to cultural heritage sites. This involves creating detailed records of the current state of each site, including structural integrity, historical significance, and the extent of damage. Engaging with international organizations such as UNESCO, ICOMOS (International Council on Monuments and Sites), and other cultural heritage bodies to provide technical expertise, funding, and advocacy. International collaboration can also facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices for heritage restoration.

The reconstruction plan should involving the local communities, historians, and cultural experts in the restoration process. Their intimate knowledge of the sites and their significance can guide culturally sensitive restoration practices. Community involvement also fosters a sense of ownership and pride in the restored heritage.

Local craftsmen, architects, and conservationists can be recruited and trained to participate in the heritage restoration efforts. Building local capacity ensures the sustainability of preservation efforts and empowers the community to maintain and protect their heritage.

4.2.5 Handling the Bodies of the Deceased before and During the Reconstruction

An often overlooked but crucial aspect of the reconstruction process is the dignified handling of the bodies of the deceased. The extensive loss of life since the conflict's escalation

on October 7th has left many families in grief, seeking closure. Managing the retrieval, identification, and burial of the deceased is essential not only for public health reasons but also for the psychological well-being of the surviving community members.

Properly handling the deceased must involve local authorities, international organizations, and community leaders to establish protocols and facilities. This process includes the respectful recovery of bodies from the rubble, identification through available records and DNA analysis, and ensuring culturally appropriate and dignified burial practices. Addressing this sensitive issue is vital for the healing and reconciliation process within the community, enabling families to mourn their loved ones with dignity and respect.

5.0 MAPPING GAZA RECONSTRUCTION CONSTRAINTS

5.1 Purpose for Mapping Gaza Reconstruction Constraints

Mapping the constraints faced in the reconstruction of Gaza is essential for several reasons, enabling a more strategic, efficient, and effective rebuilding process. Understanding these constraints helps in identifying the most pressing issues, prioritizing resources, and designing realistic and achievable plans.

Mapping constraints helps identify the main barriers to reconstruction efforts, such as the ongoing Israeli blockade, political instability, lack of resources, and security concerns. Understanding these barriers is crucial for developing strategies to overcome or mitigate their impact. By clearly understanding the constraints, stakeholders can better allocate resources where they are most needed. This ensures that limited resources such as funding, construction materials, and human capital are used efficiently and effectively, addressing the most critical areas first.

By mapping the constraints allows for the prioritization of reconstruction projects. This ensures that essential infrastructure, such as housing, healthcare, and educational facilities, are rebuilt first, addressing the immediate needs of the population and laying the foundation for long-term recovery. Detailed mapping provides valuable data that can inform policy and decision-making at local, national, and international levels. It helps policymakers understand the ground realities and develop targeted interventions that address specific constraints and challenges.

Understanding the constraints helps improve coordination among various stakeholders, including local authorities, international organizations, NGOs, and donor agencies. It fosters collaboration by aligning efforts, avoiding duplication, and ensuring that all parties are working towards common goals. Mapping constraints allows for the anticipation of potential challenges and the development of contingency plans. This proactive approach ensures that reconstruction efforts can continue smoothly even in the face of unforeseen obstacles or changes in the situation on the ground.

This mapping exercise would help to provide a baseline for monitoring and evaluating the progress of reconstruction efforts. It enables the assessment of whether strategies are effective in overcoming barriers and achieving desired outcomes, facilitating continuous improvement. Understanding the constraints faced by local communities helps in designing reconstruction efforts that not only address immediate needs but also build long-term resilience. This involves creating sustainable infrastructure, fostering economic opportunities, and strengthening social cohesion.

The mapping also would help to share the information with all stakeholders which would promote transparency and accountability. It ensures that the challenges and progress of reconstruction efforts are visible to the public and that resources are being used appropriately and effectively. Finally, the detailed mapping of constraints provides donors with a clear understanding of the needs and challenges, encouraging targeted and sustained support. It helps in building trust and ensuring that donor contributions are making a tangible impact on the ground.

5.2 Setting up the Mapping of Gaza Reconstruction Framework

Based on the literature review and the application of certain Gaza reconstruction constraints the authors put forwards specific 3-dimensional thinking map that need to be taken into consideration to enhance the outcome of foresighted Gaza reconstruction, as shown in Figure (1).

5.2.1 Defining Reconstruction Scope

This focus starts with reviewing of Gaza Infrastructure and then pre-assessment of direct damage to Gaza's infrastructure.

5.2.2 Donor Constraints

This part focus on the donors of Gaza reconstruction projects starting from the conferences till the donors accountable commitment and then possibilities for donor fatigue.

5.2.3 Socioplottical Reconstruction Constraints

This constraint dimension focus on the recognition of Palestinian rights, besides the results of the consistent attack on UNRWA since October 7th, 2023 and all what it take to help prioritise humanitarian access.

5.2.4 Socioeconomic Assets Constraints

The mapping of the socioeconomic constraints in relevance to Gaza reconstruction requires an appreciation of the Gaza natural, social, heritage, health, and physical assets, besides the electricity and water supply,

Figure (1): 3-D Constructs for Gaza Reconstruction

The authors believe that with such type of thinking approach the impact of the reconstruction on the quality of life vs. the speed of reconstruction can be tremendous and exponential. Since the learning from the previous wars reconstruction efforts would be optimised and the risks would be mitigated or alleviated. This is reflected in Figure (2)

Figure (2): Illustrate potential mapping that can help develop exponential curve that deliver reconstruction for Gaza based on the quality of life vs. the speed of reconstruction.

6.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The reconstruction of Gaza after the October 7th, 2023 is a complex challenge that requires mapping its strategic inputs to meet the demands of the unprecedented destruction combined with historical barriers that come from the Israeli blockade. This study also saw the other challenges that would lead to donors fatigue and require a radical shift in planning and implementation. The author highlighted the importance of learning from past reconstruction efforts, addressing socio-political and humanitarian challenges while taking into consideration Gaza socioeconomic concerns.

The mapping shows that for an effective reconstruction, we must prioritize the immediate humanitarian needs of the population, including housing, healthcare, and basic services, while also laying the groundwork for long-term economic stability and social cohesion. This involves physical rebuilding, addressing psychological trauma, and fostering a sense of community. The international community’s role is crucial, and renewed diplomatic efforts, increased recognition of Palestinian rights, and robust support for key organizations like the UNRWA are essential.

In summary, the reconstruction of Gaza must include a dedicated focus on preserving and restoring all the main assets of the community, i.e., the social, natural, physical, and cultural assets. By doing so, the community can restore its historical continuity, foster further resilience pride, and leverage reconstruction as a cornerstone for the sustenance of resilience. Thus, this study calls for a holistic and human-centered reconstruction process. Also, the possibility of donors’ fatigue remains a significant threat, and overcoming it will require transparent governance, effective use of funds, and demonstrable progress. Ensuring local representation in planning and execution, alongside robust international coordination, can help build trust and encourage sustained support.

Ultimately, the path to a stable and thriving Gaza lies in a coordinated effort that addresses both immediate needs and long-term development goals, ensuring a human-centred recovery that respects the rights and aspirations of the Palestinian people.

References

- 1) AlJazeera. (2024). ‘Moral failure’: US House approves bill that would ban UNRWA funding. News- Israel-Palestine conflict. Retrieved on July 15, 2024, from <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/22/moral-failure-us-house-approves-bill-that-would-ban-unrwa-funding>
- 2) AlJazeera. (2024). Mapping which countries recognise Palestine in 2024. News- Israel-Palestine conflict. Retrieved on July 15, 2024, from <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/5/22/mapping-which-countries-recognise-palestine-in-2024>
- 3) Barakat, S., Zyck, H, Hunt, J (2009). The Reconstruction of Gaza, Post War Reconstruction and Development Unit (PWRDU), York University.
- 4) Barakat, S.; Shaban, O. (2015). Back to Gaza: A New Approach to Reconstruction. Brookings Doha Center.
- 5) Barakat, S., Milton, S., Elkahlout, G. (2021). Rebuilding Gaza: The need for a radical shift in Reconstruction Strategy. Center for Conflict and Humanitarian Studies.
- 6) Barakat, S., Milton, S., & Elkahlout, G. (2018). The Gaza reconstruction mechanism: Old wine in new bottlenecks. *Journal of Intervention and Statebuilding*, 12(2), 208-227.
- 7) Barakat, S., Milton, S., & Elkahlout, G. (2020). Reconstruction under siege: the Gaza Strip since 2007. *Disasters*, 44(3), 477-498.
- 8) Buheji, M (2024). Addressing Human Factors in Gaza: Challenges and Solutions for Post-War Recovery, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(3), pp. 35-45.
- 9) Buheji, M and Hasan, a (2024). Capitalising on the ‘Social Capital’ That Would Accelerate the Collective Wealth of Gaza, *International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development (IJSSRD)*, 6(1), pp. 134-152.
- 10) Buheji, M and Mushimiyimana, E (2024) (GAZA 2024) Revising the ‘Reasons to Live’ An Assessment of Current Scenarios & Foresighted Future, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(1), 2024, pp. 209-229.
- 11) Buheji, M; Al-Muhannadi, K (2023) Mitigating Risks of Environmental Impacts on Gaza - Review of Precautions & Solutions post (2023 War), *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology*, 14(7), pp. 15-47
- 12) Enshassi, A. (2000). Environmental concerns for construction growth in Gaza Strip. *Building and Environment*, 35(3), 273-279.
- 13) Felsberger, S. (2015) Gaza: Destructive Reconstruction. *Focus, AIES*
- 14) Geneva Declaration Secretariat. (2008). Global Burden of Armed Violence. Retrieved on July 17, 2024, from <https://www.refworld.org/reference/research/gds/2008/en/64390>

- 15) Hochberg, M. (2016). The Five Factors Slowing Gaza Reconstruction. Institute for Near East Policy.
- 16) IMF. (2023). West Bank and Gaza: Report to the AD HOC Liaison Committee. International Monetary Fund. Middle East and Central Asia Department. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5089/9798400253089.002>
- 17) Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC). (2024). Gaza Strip: Acute Food Insecurity Situation for 15 February - 15 March 2024 and Projection for 16 March - 15 July 2024. Retrieved on July 15, 2024, from <https://www.ipcinfo.org/ipc-country-analysis/details-map/en/c/1156872/?iso3=PSE>
- 18) Milton, S., Elkahlout, G., & Attallah, S. (2024). Shrinking reconstruction space in the Gaza Strip: rebuilding after the 2021 and 2022 wars. *Conflict, Security & Development*, 24(1), 49–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14678802.2024.2314034>
- 19) OCHA. (2022). Gaza Strip | The humanitarian impact of 15 years of the blockade - June 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.ochaopt.org/content/gaza-strip-humanitarian-impact-15-years-blockade-june-2022>
- 20) OCHA. (n.d). Data on casualties. Retrieved from <https://www.ochaopt.org/data/casualties>
- 21) Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics. Retrieved July 2nd, 2024, from <https://www.pcbs.gov.ps/default.aspx>
- 22) Phusavat, K and Buheji, M (2024) Mapping Informal Learning for Displaced Learners during the War on Gaza 2023- Application of Situated Cognition, *International Journal of Learning and Development*, Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 1-16.
- 23) Shorrab, A; Nassef, M; Subhi, A; Giwa, B; Buheji, M (2024) Health in the Crossfire - Analyzing and Mitigating the Multifaceted Health Risks of the 2023 War on Gaza, *Public Health Research*, 14(1): 1-11.
- 24) ReliefWeb (2024, 24 April). 200 days of military attack on Gaza: A horrific death toll amid intl. failure to stop Israel's genocide of Palestinians – Occupied Palestinian territory. [News and Press release]. Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/report/occupied-palestinian-territory/200-days-military-attack-gaza-horrific-death-toll-amid-intl-failure-stop-israels-genocide-palestinians-enar>
- 25) The World Bank, the European Union, the United Nations. (2024). Gaza Strip - Interim Damage Assessment. Summary Note – March 29, 2024. Preliminary estimates - October 2023 to January 2024. Retrieved from <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/14e309cd34e04e40b90eb19afa7b5d15-0280012024/original/Gaza-Interim-Damage-Assessment-032924-Final.pdf>
- 26) Tayeh, B. A., Al Hallaq, K., Alaloul, W. S., & Kuhail, A. R. (2018). Factors affecting the success of construction projects in Gaza Strip. *The Open Civil Engineering Journal*, 12(1).
- 27) UN Office Geneva. 10 000 people feared buried under the rubble in Gaza. Retrieved July, 10,2024, from <https://www.ungeneva.org/en/news-media/news/2024/05/93055/10000-people-feared-buried-under-rubble-gaza>

- 28) UNCTAD. (2020). the Economic Costs of the Israeli Occupation for the Palestinian People: The Impoverishment of Gaza under Blockade. United Nations Publications. UNCTAD/GDS/APP/2020/1.
- 29) UNCTAD. (2024). Preliminary Assessment of the Economic Impact of the Destruction in Gaza and Prospects for Economic Recovery. UNCTAD Rapid Assessment. Retrieved from <https://unctad.org/publication/preliminary-assessment-economic-impact-destruction-gaza-and-prospects-economic-recovery>
- 30) UNDP. (2021). Gaza 2021 Infrastructure Damage Assessment Report. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/migration/ps/UNDP-papp-research-GazaInfra.pdf>
- 31) UNESCWA & UNDP. (2024). Gaza war: Expected socioeconomic impacts on the State of Palestine - Update (May 2024). Retrieved from https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2024-05/2400257e-gaza_war-_expected_socioeconomic_impacts-pb.pdf
- 32) UNESCWA. (2024). War on Gaza: twenty-first century's deadliest 100 days?. ESCWA Publication: E/ESCWA/CL6.GCP/2023/Policy brief.3